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“A PROFESSIONAL TEACHER, A TEACHER OF LOVE”

I am a professional teacher,
I must make my learners learn,
I am a model of moral values and dignity,
I am a prototype of reputation and integrity.

I am committed to education,
Teaching is my forever passion,
Loving what I teach,
And loving whom I teach.

I am a coadjutor of learning,
But my mission is not just to teach!
My mission is to make my learners learn,
Out of my ways of teaching.

I must never quit and stop learning,
Pursuing higher degree of education and being in school again,
'Cause the more I have, the more I can share,
Yeah! That's the essence of being a teacher.

On bigger money, I don't care,
'Cause there's no millionaire,
On being a teacher,
My sole concern is to make my learners learn.

Who said being a teacher is easy!
Is it easy to speak continually for eight hours a day?
Making lesson plans every night,
It was like a never-ending fight!

But as my philosophy goes,
You will never get tired of the things you do,
As long as you do everything in love,

Yeah! That makes us every day to stand!

To us, all the hardships are nothing,
Just to see our students are developing,
Just to see our learners are learning,
At the end of the day, it is the most satisfying thing.

